

Abstract Scenarios: Task instructions and scene settings

Below the Abstract Scenarios are described, and the unity study setup for this part is provided as a unity package (abstractStudySetup.unitypackage) along with this file.

Task instructions for Object-Referenced

Simple (a)

- 1) Distance between Green Cube and Red Capsule -> Blue Sphere(E)
- 2) Red Capsule(B) -> Green Cube(D) and Blue Sphere(F)
- 3) Time -> Yellow Sphere(E)

Partially Occluded (b)

- 1) Red Cube(B) -> Green Sphere(F) and Green Cube(E)
- 2) Yellow Sphere(A) -> Red Sphere(D) and Yellow Cube(E)
- 3) Distance between Pink Cube and Yellow Cube -> Red Cube(D)
- 4) Time -> Blue Cube(F)

Varying Size (c)

- 1) Green Cube(A) -> Red Cube(D)
- 2) Pink Cube(B) -> Green Cube(F)
- 3) Blue Sphere(A) -> Red Sphere(D)
- 4) Green Sphere(C) -> Blue Cube(F)
- 5) Yellow Cube(B) -> Pink Capsule(E)

Distant (d)

- 1) Green Cube(B) -> Blue Cube(D) and Red Capsule(E)
- 2) Blue Cube(A) -> Red Capsule(F)
- 3) Pink Cube(C) -> Yellow Cube(F)
- 4) Red Capsule(A) -> Yellow Cube(E)
- 5) Green Cube(A) -> Pink Cube(F)
- 6) Distance between Yellow Capsule and Pink Cube -> Green Capsule(E) and Yellow Cube(D)
- 7) Time -> Red Capsule(D) and Blue Cube(F)

Task instructions for Surround-Referenced

Simple

- 1) Distance between Yellow Cube and Blue Capsule -> Green Sphere(E)
- 2) Blue Capsule(B) -> Yellow Cube(D) and Green Sphere(F)
- 3) Time -> Red Sphere(E)

Partially Occluded

- 1) Yellow Cube(B) -> Pink Sphere(F) and Blue Cube(E)
- 2) Blue Sphere(A) -> Red Sphere(D) and Red Cube(E)
- 3) Distance between Green Sphere and Red Cube -> Yellow Cube(D)
- 4) Time -> Green Cube(F)

Varying Scale

- 1) Red Cube(A) -> Green Cube(D)
- 2) Blue Cube(B) -> Red Cube(F)
- 3) Red Sphere(A) -> Green Sphere(D)
- 4) Pink Sphere(C) -> Yellow Cube(F)
- 5) Pink Cube(B) -> Blue Capsule(E)

Distant

- 1) Blue Cube(B) -> Red Cube(D) and Pink Capsule(E)
- 2) Red Cube(A) -> Pink Capsule(F)
- 3) Yellow Cube(C) -> Green Cube(F)
- 4) Pink Capsule(A) -> Green Cube(E)
- 5) Blue Cube(A) -> Yellow Cube(F)
- 6) Distance between Yellow Capsule and Yellow Cube -> Green Capsule(E) and Green Cube(D)

7) Time -> Pink Capsule(D) and Red Cube(F)

Realistic Scenarios: Task descriptions and scene settings

Regarding realistic scenarios, we have used the "POLYGON Nature - Low Poly 3D Art by Synty" asset. Since it is a paid asset, we can not provide the unity scene regarding this part, however, the images of this part can be seen below. The asset can be found in the following link: <https://assetstore.unity.com/packages/3d/vegetation/trees/polygon-nature-low-poly-3d-art-by-synty-120152>

